

MULTILAYER SiC-MoSi₂ COMPOSITES PRODUCED BY TAPE CASTING

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SUMMARY

The study presents the results of the analysis of SiC-MoSi₂ composites with multilayer structure produced by tape casting. The effect of different content of SiC and MoSi₂ was investigated, as well as the result of integration of composite and SiC layers. The practicability of a Functionally Graded Material production was also considered.

Keywords: Silicon Carbide, Molybdenum Silicides, Tape Casting, Multilayer, Functionally Graded Materials

INTRODUCTION

Ceramic materials can be suited for high temperature applications, provided that their toughness and reliability could be increased. Monolithic ceramic materials are indeed subject to brittle fracture, due to the absence of means to dissipate energy during fracture. Toughness of ceramics can be raised with the introduction of weak interfaces in the material, by adding a second phase (often fibres) in the matrix or by building a multilayered structure. Weak interfaces allow the dissipation of energy during crack propagation, by means of deflection, bridging and pull-out (for fibres) and delamination (for multilayers).

Multilayered ceramics produced by tape casting and sintering are cheaper than fibre-reinforced composites, still they can have higher toughness than isotropic materials and can even show no brittle behaviour at all [1]. This can happen by cause of weak interfaces or residual stresses between layers. When the interface between layers has poor strength, crack growth can be deflected into the interface; also a porous layer can act as a weak interface [2, 3]. The difference in degree of sintering or in thermal expansion coefficient can generate residual stresses between adjacent layers of different composition; these residual stresses can be tailored to optimize the material's opposition to crack propagation.

In this work SiC-MoSi₂ composites produced by tape casting are studied. In the first stage composites with different relative content of SiC and MoSi₂ were characterized. Subsequent stages were the inclusion of composite layers with different compositions within multilayer SiC samples, and the preparation of samples made of different layers with increasing content of MoSi₂, to examine the practicability of the production of a Functionally Graded Material.

EXPERIMENTAL WORK

Samples were prepared through the following steps: slurry preparation, tape casting, solvent evaporation, specimen forming, debinding and sintering.

The slurries were obtained by dispersing ceramic powders in organic solvents and carrying out ball milling in Al_2O_3 jars with Al_2O_3 balls for about 24 h. Subsequently plasticizer and binder were added and ball milling was carried on for about 24 h. Thin sheets were produced by casting the slurry on a moving polyester film. The layer thickness was controlled by selecting proper blade gap (1 mm) and casting speed (100 mm/min). The slurry was then dried on the flat surface of tape casting apparatus for about 12 h, thus allowing the organic solvents to be completely removed by slow and controlled evaporation in air.

Base slurry was composed using α -SiC powder with Al_2O_3 (6% of SiC weight) and Y_2O_3 (4% of SiC weight) as sintering aids. These cause the sintering to occur in liquid phase at a temperature compatible with the sintering temperature of MoSi_2 . The composition of base slurry is detailed in Table 1; the resulting ceramic material was named SAY. Composite slurries were prepared replacing part of powder volume with a same volume of MoSi_2 powder; composites with 20% vol. or more of MoSi_2 were prepared both with and without Al_2O_3 and Y_2O_3 .

Table 1 – Base slurry composition.

		wt. %
solvents	ethanol	11,8
	buthanol	18,2
	tetrachloroethylene	20,7
powders	SiC	31,1
	Al_2O_3	2,1
	Y_2O_3	1,4
binder		9,6
plasticizer		5,1

SiC tapes, MoSi_2 tapes and SiC- MoSi_2 tapes were submitted to thermogravimetric analysis (TGA/SDTA Mettler-Toledo), whose results were useful to optimize the debinding treatment.

After drying, the flexible green tapes were detached from the plastic support, cut into the desired shape and stacked one upon the other to form the multilayered structure. In the first stage samples were prepared using all layers of the same material, to fully

characterize each single composite. Subsequently samples with alternating SiC and composite layers were prepared, lastly samples made of layers with increasing content of MoSi₂. The adhesion between layers was effected by painting a gluing solution made of water, ethanol and polyvinyl alcohol and by rolling with a mandrel in order to prevent the formation of air bubbles between layers.

Multilayered specimens were submitted to a debinding treatment, carried out by slow heating up to 800 °C in argon flow. The final pressureless sintering step was performed in a graphite furnace at 1950 °C for 120 min under 600 mbar argon atmosphere.

Sintered samples of SiC-MoSi₂ composites and samples with alternating SiC and composite layers were subjected to physical and mechanical analysis. Density of the samples was measured, Young's modulus was determined by the impulse excitation technique; three-point bending tests were performed with a crosshead speed of 0.1 mm/min. Finally the microstructure and chemical composition of the samples were assessed by scanning electron microscopy (SEM-FEG Assing SUPRA 25) coupled with energy dispersive spectroscopy (EDS Oxford).

The samples made of layers with increasing content of MoSi₂ were debinded and sintered in various conditions to determine the best process parameters.

Figure 1 – Thermogravimetric analysis on green tapes.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Preliminary Analysis on Green Tapes

Figure 1 shows the results of thermogravimetric analysis on SiC tapes, MoSi₂ tapes and SiC-MoSi₂ composites of different composition. It can be noted that the presence of

MoSi₂ lowers the temperature of decompositions of organics. For the whole of analyzed materials organics decomposition takes place almost completely between 200 and 500 °C. These findings brought to choose a conveniently low heating rate during debinding in this temperature interval, to let the gaseous species flow out without damaging the powder structure.

SiC-MoSi₂ Composites

In Figure 2 SEM images of the fracture surface of sintered multilayers are reported; three SiC-MoSi₂ composites, with different content in MoSi₂ and with sintering aids for SiC (Al₂O₃ and Y₂O₃), are shown.

Figure 2 – SEM images of fracture surface of sintered composites: left BSE (dark SiC, light MoSi₂), right SE. (a) 10MoSi₂-90SAY, (b) 30MoSi₂-70SAY, (c) 50MoSi₂-50SAY.

Figure 3 – Relative density (a) and bending strength (b) of SiC-MoSi₂ composites (samples of 10 layers).

Figure 4 – Bending strength of samples with alternating layers of pure SiC and of 60%SiC-40%MoSi₂ composite, compared with that of SiC and composite.

Results of density measurements and of 3-point bending tests are summarized in Figure 3, with varying MoSi_2 content and with or without sintering aids. Measures showed that with high content of MoSi_2 mechanical properties decrease, while the presence of sintering aids does not produce significant effect. Low bending strength of composites richer in MoSi_2 suggests that the selected sintering temperature was too high for this phase.

Samples with Alternating SiC and Composite Layers

Bending strengths of some samples with alternating layers of pure SiC and layers of SiC- MoSi_2 composites are reported in Figure 4 and compared with the values for samples made of only SiC layers and only composite layers. These results showed that the interposition of composite layers allows for the tailoring of the mechanical strength of the material.

Figure 5 – SEM images of a sample with layers of SiC and of SiC- MoSi_2 composite; (a) BSE, (b) EDS map for Mo

Towards a Functionally Graded Material

In Figure 5 a micrograph of a sample with layers of SiC (and sintering aids Al_2O_3 and Y_2O_3) and of SiC-MoSi₂ composite with increasing MoSi₂ content is shown.

Layers of different materials have different thermal expansion coefficient and different debinding and sintering rates. To prevent curling or breaking of samples, debinding and sintering parameters needed to be adjusted. The weights put on samples during debinding and sintering treatments were optimized; the temperature rise during debinding was slowed down; two isothermal steps were introduced during heating and cooling at the start and at the end of sintering. The effects of these adjustments are qualitatively shown in Figure 6.

Figure 6 – Qualitative results of process adjustments; (a) effect of debinding modifications, (b) effect of sintering modifications.

CONCLUSIONS

A wide range of multilayer SiC-MoSi₂ composites produced by tape casting was characterized. Best results in term of density and mechanical strength were obtained with less than 40% vol. of MoSi₂. The interposition of SiC-MoSi₂ composite layers with fairly high content of MoSi₂ within SiC multilayer samples provided however good mechanical strength. Finally, tape casting technique showed good potential for the production of a Functionally Graded Material.

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